

Influence of nitrogen fertilizer and cattle manure on the vegetative growth and tuber production of potato

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ABSTRACT: In order to study the Influence of nitrogen (N) fertilizer and cattle manure on the vegetative growth and tuber production of potato, a field experiment was conducted in April 2008 in Iran, with factorial arrangement based on randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. Treatment groups consisted of the administration of nitrogen fertilizer at three concentration levels (50, 100 and 150 Kg h⁻¹) and cattle manure at four levels (5, 10, 15 and 20 tons h⁻¹). From 45th to 105th day after emergence (DAE), plant height and Leaf Area Index (LAI) were measured every 15 days. Furthermore, at the end of the growth season, tuber yield was calculated. Results showed that, in all sampling times, plant height and LAI were increased significantly by increasing N fertilizer. In addition, the LAI showed significant differences in relation to different concentrations of cattle manure. In the same way, the plant heights showed a significant rise with the increasing concentrations of cattle manure at the 45th, 60th, 75th and 90th DAE. The integrated use of nitrogen fertilizer and cattle manure increased LAI significantly (at the 45th, 75th and 90th DAE). Also, the combined effects of cattle manure and N fertilizer on plant heights were significant at the 60th, 75th, 90th and 105th DAE. Furthermore, results of tuber yield showed that, Nitrogen fertilizer, Cattle manure and their combination had highly significant effects on tuber yield. In this experiment maximum amount of tuber yield (36.8 tons ha⁻¹) was obtained by 20 tons ha⁻¹ Cattle manure+150 kg N ha⁻¹.

Key words: Solanum tuberosum, Leaf Area Index, N Fertilizer, Organic fertilizer, Plant height, Tuber yield.

ABBREVIATIONS: C Cattle Manure, DAE Day after emergence, LAI Leaf Area Index, N Nitrogen

INTRODUCTION

Potato (Tuber) is an important crop in Iran and has effective role in human nutrition (Haj Seyed Hadi, 2006). The tuber production can be affected by the developmental dynamics of plants' parts (Struik, 2007 b). There is an association between above-ground and under-ground organs of the potato plant (Struik, 2007 a). So, the final tuber yield can be affected by the situation of above-ground organs in the growth season (Struik, 2007 b).

The plant growth involves various environmental and agronomical factors, such as water, temperature, light, nutrients, and etc. (Liu et al., 2004; Yadav, 2008; Yuan et al., 2003). Among these factors, nitrogen nutrient plays a special role in the growth, production and quality of potatoes (Lisińska and Leszczyński, 1989; Westermann and Kleinkopf, 1985).

The nitrogen (N) is a vital nutrient for the activity of plant organs. It is a fraction of many components such as; amino acids, nucleic acids, chlorophyll and etc. Thus, plant growth can be affected by the amount of nitrogen (Najm et al., 2012a; Taiz and Zeiger, 2002). Previous studies have shown that nitrogen fertilizer can increase the growth

characteristics, such as; plant height, shoot dry matter, and Leaf Area Index (LAI) (Biemond and Vos, 1992; Hay and Walker, 1989; Honeycutt et al., 1996; Sattelmacher et al., 1990; Sincik et al., 2008; Vos and Biemond, 1992).

Although, appropriate use of nitrogen fertilizer can lead to the achievement of optimum canopy development and subsequently increase tuber yield, the excessive use of it can lead to delayed maturity and the competition between sink and source and occasionally less yield (Hay and Walker, 1989; Kumar et al., 2007; Westermann and Kleinkopf, 1985). Furthermore, although some researchers mentioned that, conventional use of chemical inputs can increase tuber yield, inordinate use of nitrogen leads to its negative effects on the environment, public health and tuber quality (Goffart et al., 2008; Najm et al., 2011; Najm et al., 2012b). Despite these negative effects, the use of chemical nitrogen has increased remarkably during decades (Freire and Sá, 2006). So, the development of new methods using the appropriate concentration of N fertilizer has become necessary for potato producers, which can encourage them to use other nutrient sources as well (Al-Moshileh and Motawei, 2005; Goffart et al., 2008).

The animal manure (such as cattle manure) is another source of nitrogen and other nutrients, which can decrease the demand of chemical fertilizer, and it has been used for many centuries to increase soil fertility (Darzi, 2012; Kolay, 2007; Mathers and Stewart, 1984; Mir and Quadri, 2009; Tagoe et al., 2008; Whalen and Chang, 2001; White et al., 2007). Except for the supply of nitrogen fraction, animal manure can improve chemical, physical and biological characteristics of soil (Benke et al., 2008; Darzi and Haj Seyd Hadi, 2012; Dong and Shu, 2004; Najm et al., 2012a; Rodriguez et al., 2001; Winterhalder et al., 1974). Many researchers have mentioned the beneficial effects of organic fertilizer including the increase of hydraulic conductivity, raising the water holding capacity, changing the soil pH (increase or decrease in the pH, depending on soil type and characteristics of organic fertilizer), elevating the soil aggregation and water infiltration, reducing the frequency of plant diseases and etc. (Conn and Lazarovits, 1999; Dong and Shu, 2004; Eghball and Power; Olson and Papworth, 2006; Tagoe et al., 2008). So, the use of animal manure has been reported as a potential factor for better vegetative growth and increased tuber yield (Abou-Hussein et al., 2003 a; Abou-Hussein et al., 2003 b; Al-Moshileh and Motawei, 2005; Jayramaiah et al., 2005).

The positive effects of organic manure on the plant height, shoot dry matter and LAI have been previously reported (Abou-Hussein et al., 2003 a; Alam et al., 2007; Jayramaiah et al., 2005; Powon et al., 2006).

The present study determines the combined and comparative effects of cattle manure and N fertilizer on the LAI and plant height of potatoes in the growth season and potato tuber yield at harvest time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The field experiment, in the factorial arrangement, based on Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications was laid out in April 2008 at the Agricultural Experiment Station of Islamic Azad University, Roudehen Branch, Tehran, Iran (35° 40' N latitude, 51° 57' E longitude and the altitude of 1827 m above the sea level). Treatment groups consisted of cattle manure at four different concentrations (5, 10, 15 and 20 tons ha⁻¹) and 50, 100 and 150 Kg ha⁻¹ of N fertilizer from the urea source.

The experimental soil was a clay loam with 1.95% organic carbon and the pH of 7.9. The P₂O₅ (available), K₂O (available), total nitrogen, Mn, Fe, Zn and Cu contents were observed to be 25.2 ppm, 490 ppm, 0.167%, 11 mg kg⁻¹, 2.6 mg kg⁻¹, 1.1 mg kg⁻¹ and 0.8 mg kg⁻¹ in March, 2008, respectively.

Potatoes of Agria variety were planted in the field on 21st April, 2008. The plot size was considered to be 15 m². Tuber seeds were hand planted in the furrows of four rows with the depth of 15 cm, inter-row spacing of 75 cm and the intra-row spacing of 25 cm. The irrigation was conducted via sprinkler irrigation system. Cattle manure was analyzed before use and its entire rate was applied before plantation (Table 1). Nitrogen fertilizer was applied during three phases of tuber cultivation: planting, germination and earthing up.

From 45th to 105th day after emergence (DAE), samples were collected (three random potato plants from each plot) every 15 days. Plant heights were measured from the base to apex of the main shoot. Leaf area was calculated with an automated leaf area meter. LAI was estimated by dividing the total leaf area of the sample by ground areaharvested (Scholes et al., 1995; Zelalem et al., 2009).

Tubers were manually harvested in a 2 m of the two middle rows, excluding 0.5 m from each end of plots, on 31 October 2008. After harvesting, the total tuber yield was determined for each plot.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed using the General Linear Model (GLM) procedure of SAS 6.12 (SAS Institute, 1996, Cary, NC, USA). Graphs for cattle manure and nitrogen fertilizer were obtained by using Prism 5 for Windows (Graph Pad Software Inc. 2007, San Diego, CA). For the determination of interaction between nitrogen fertilizer and cattle manure, the means were compared using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (P< 0.05).

RESULTS

Nitrogen Fertilizer

The present results show that during all experiments, LAI was increased very significantly by increasing the amount of nitrogen fertilizer (Table 2). Although, during early growth season, LAI showed minor difference within the treatments containing different concentrations of nitrogen fertilizer, which increased after 60th up to 105th DAE. On the 105th DAE, the maximum LAI (5.811) was obtained after the administration of 150 kg N ha⁻¹ (Figure 1).

Also, in the all sampling times the plant height demonstrated significant change after the addition of nitrogen fertilizer (Table 2). Figure 1 demonstrates that during all experiments, the maximum plant height was obtained after the administration of 150 kg N ha⁻¹, which was significantly more than the heights seen for other treatment groups. However, during the early growing season, 50 and 100 kg N ha⁻¹ showed a slight difference in plant height as compared to the group receiving higher N concentration. In this experiment, at the 105th DAE, the amounts of plant height were as follows after the administration of 50, 100 and 150 Kg N ha⁻¹: 67.65, 74.32, and 83.77 cm, respectively (Figure 1).

Furthermore, results of tuber yields showed a very significant differences in response to nitrogen fertilizer (Table 2). Tuber yield increased with increasing nitrogen fertilizer, and the amounts of tuber yield in 50, 100, 150 Kg N ha⁻¹ were 26.50, 32.66 and 35.10 ton ha⁻¹ respectively.

Cattle Manure

Table 2 shows that the cattle manure had a very significant effect on the LAI in the all sampling times. However, at the early growth season (45th and 60th) there were minor differences between 10, 15 and 20 tons manure ha⁻¹, the lowest amount of manure (5 tons manure ha⁻¹) showed specific differences with other groups. Although, at the 75th and 90th DAE, the LAI demonstrated an increase with the increasing concentration of cattle manure, at the 105th DAE, there were no specific differences in the LAI between the groups receiving 10 and 15 tons manure ha⁻¹. But there were distinctive differences among other treatments at this time (Figure 2).

Also, during the growth season, the cattle manure demonstrated a significant effect on the plant height (except for the 105th DAE) (Table 2). So, during the growth season, the maximum amount of plant height was obtained using 20 ton ha⁻¹ cattle manure. While, 5, 10 and 15 ton manure ha⁻¹ showed a slight difference in the plant height during the early growth season. But only 10 and 15 ton manure ha⁻¹ showed similar trends (Figure 2). Also, in this experiment tuber yield was affected by cattle manure very significantly (Table 2), and the amounts of tuber yields were as follows after the administration of 5, 10, 15 and 20 ton ha⁻¹: 25.42, 29.76, 35.15, and 35.34 ton ha⁻¹ respectively.

Combined administration of cattle manure and nitrogen fertilizer

The LAI was affected significantly by the combined administration of cattle manure and nitrogen fertilizer at the 45th, 75th and 90th DAE (Table 2). Data presented in Table 3 show that the LAI increased approximately by increasing the combined concentration of nitrogen fertilizer and cattle manure. In this experiment, the maximum amounts of shoot dry matter were obtained at the 45th DAE (1.141) and 75th DAE (5.360) following the administration of 20 tons ha⁻¹ cattle manure + 150 kg N ha⁻¹, whereas, at 90th DAE (6.149) was obtained by 15 tons ha⁻¹ cattle manure + 150 kg N ha⁻¹. But in all times, the Duncan's Multiple Range Test did not show significant difference between these two treatment groups ($p \leq 0.05$).

The combined effects of cattle manure and nitrogen fertilizer were significant for the plant height at the 60th, 75th, and 105th DAE, whereas, a considerable difference was seen for the treatments at the 90th DAE (Table 2). Table 3 shows that the plant heights increased approximately by increasing the amount of nitrogen fertilizer and cattle manure during the all sampling times. The maximum amounts of plant height at the 60th DAE (54.833 cm) and 90th DAE (87.733 cm) were obtained by using 20 tons ha⁻¹ cattle manure + 150 kg N ha⁻¹ N fertilizer. While, at

the 75thDAE (73 cm) and 105thDAE (100.544 cm), the maximum plant heights were recorded after the combined administration of 15 tons ha⁻¹ cattle manure + 150 kg N ha⁻¹ N fertilizer. The Duncan's Multiple Range Test did not show significant difference between the two treatment groups (p≤0.05).

The recent results have shown that the tuber yield was increased very significantly by increasing the integrated use of cattle manure and N fertilizer (Table 2). In this experiment, maximum tuber yield (36.8 ton ha⁻¹) was obtained by using 20 tons ha⁻¹ Cattle manure+150 kg N ha⁻¹ (Table 3).

Figure 1. Plant height and LAI as a function of time and nitrogen fertilizer (50 Kg Nitrogen ha⁻¹ ●; 100 Kg Nitrogen ha⁻¹ ■; and 150 Kg Nitrogen ha⁻¹ ▲).

Figure 2. Plant height and LAI as a function of time and cattle manure (5 ton cattle manure ha⁻¹ ●; 10 ton cattle manure ha⁻¹ ■; 15 ton cattle manure ▲ and 20 ton cattle manure ha⁻¹ ◆).

Table 1. Some properties of the manure samples used in the present study.

Parameters	Organic carbon (%)	C/N (%)	Total N (%)	Total P (%)	Total K (%)	Total Mg (%)	Total Ca (%)	Total elemental content (mg kg ⁻¹)			
								Fe	Mn	Cu	Zn
Cow manure	46.2	22.91	2.016	0.72	2.8	1.2	3.5	185.3	150	17.4	144.6

Table 2. Analysis of variance for Plant height, LAI and Tuber yields.

Source of variation	df	Day After Emergence (DAE)										Tuber Yield
		45 th		60 th		75 th		90 th		105 th		
		Plant height	LAI	Plant height	LAI	Plant height	LAI	Plant height	LAI	Plant height	LAI	
N	2	** 142.38	** 0.4557	** 318.64	** 1.9563	** 521.06	** 5.0707	** 992.11	** 7.0298	* 787.19	** 8.617	** 235.914
C	3	** 123.48	** 0.5289	** 305.72	** 1.8227	** 558.22	** 5.2876	** 421.22	** 4.3833	ns 91.57	** 2.1867	** 204.143
N × C	6	ns 32.37	* 0.0266	* 31.44	ns 0.1677	* 156.49	* 0.7291	** 416.68	* 1.5477	* 468.20	ns 0.9408	** 85.366
Error Mean Square	2	24.72	0.0088	10.94	0.0775	54.59	0.2626	85.48	0.5986	139.62	0.3704	18.195
C.V		16.67	12.67	7.49	15.04	13.58	13.86	13.80	17.00	15.70	12.34	13.57

**P<0.01; *P<0.05; ns = Non-significant N: Nitrogen fertilizer C: Cattle manure.

Table 3. Combined effect of cattle manure and nitrogen on the Plant height, LAI and Tuber yields.

Cattle Manure ton ha ⁻¹	Nitrogen Fertilizer kg ha ⁻¹	Plant height (cm)				LAI			Tuber Yield (ton ha ⁻¹)
		Day After Emergence							
		60 th	75 th	90 th	105 th	45 th	75 th	90 th	
5	50	31.000f	45.000de	65.216bcd	77.508b	0.315f	2.825d	3.817bcd	13.857e
	100	39.500de	46.667de	57.815cde	68.500bc	0.453ef	2.726d	3.859bcd	27.327bc
	150	45.167bcd	44.000de	51.869de	67.548b	0.470ef	3.015cd	3.919bcd	35.084ab
10	50	34.000ef	45.000de	60.250cde	72.628bc	0.391f	2.628d	3.371cd	23.068c
	100	40.750d	55.500cde	69.392bcd	74.260bc	0.787d	3.182cd	4.191bcd	30.801ab
	150	49.000abc	57.333bcd	73.167abc	78.345b	0.964bc	4.143b	4.984ab	35.422ab
15	50	41.000d	42.000e	45.868e	52.029c	0.609e	2.726d	2.814d	36.639a
	100	43.733cd	51.667cde	68.862bcd	74.770b	0.889cd	4.598ab	5.118ab	35.706a
	150	50.000ab	73.000a	86.620a	100.544a	1.089ab	4.766ab	6.149a	33.117ab
20	50	52.333a	60.626abc	58.837cde	68.440bc	0.808cd	3.916bc	4.810abc	32.437ab
	100	48.833abc	61.333abc	78.491ab	79.760b	0.978abc	4.506ab	5.868a	36.788a
	150	54.833a	70.833ab	87.733a	88.645ab	1.141a	5.360a	5.712a	36.800a

Values in a column with the same letter were not statistically different at $p \leq 0.05$ by Duncan test.

DISCUSSION

Nitrogen Fertilizer

Nitrogen is an important nutrient for the activity of plant organs (Taiz and Zeiger, 2002). Nitrogen fertilizer can increase N uptake and subsequently its concentration in the leaves (Millard and Marshall, 1986; Shah et al., 2004). An increased N content stimulates the photosynthetic capacity by the elevation of the content of stromal and thylakoid proteins in leaves (Mauromicale et al., 2006). Previous studies have mentioned the positive effect of

nitrogen supply in the form of increased leaf expansion and stem branching capacity (Mauromicale et al., 2006; Vos, 1995; Vos and Biemond, 1992). Thus, the shoot dry matter, LAI and plant height, and subsequently the total crop yield can be increased by increasing the concentration of nitrogen fertilizer up to an optimal level. These results are in agreement with the previous reports (Biemond and Vos, 1992; Hay and Walker, 1989; Honeycutt et al., 1996; Sattelmacher et al., 1990; Sincik et al., 2008; Vos and Biemond, 1992).

Cattle Manure

Cattle manure used in this experiment had relevant nutrient content (Table 1). Also, the administration of organic manure to the soil may enhance the solubility of some nutrients such as zinc and phosphorus (Khan and Joergensen, 2009; Swietlik, 1999). On the other hand, the supply of animals manure can result in the improvement of soil characteristics (physical and biological). The increase of the above mentioned soil nutrients and other factors can encourage shoot growth and elevate the metabolism of photosynthesis (Abou-Hussein et al., 2003 b).

In the same way, Jayramaiah et al. (2005) have shown that the increased plant height, shoot number, leaves area, and total dry matter accumulation were obtained by the application of appropriate amount of farm yard manure. Abou-Hussein et al. (2003a, b) have observed that the fresh weight of potato shoots, plant height, and tuber yield were increased significantly by the combined administration of cattle and chicken manure (Abou-Hussein et al., 2003 a). In the same way, Powon et al. (2006) showed that, the amount of LAI can increase with increasing organic fertilizer.

Combined administration of cattle manure and nitrogen fertilizer

The increases of plant height, LAI and tuber yield with the integrated use of cattle manure and nitrogen fertilizer were due to their positive effects, as mentioned above. The current results are in-line with those of Alam et al. (2007), which demonstrated that the maximum amounts of plant height, shoot dry matter and Tuber yield of potato were obtained by the combined administration of vermin compost and chemical fertilizer (Alam et al., 2007).

It can be concluded from the present study that the separate application of nitrogen fertilizer and cattle manure has a positive effect on plant height and LAI in growth season but their combined use has more beneficial effect on the above-mentioned parameters. The present experiment has also concluded that the maximum amount of tuber yield (36.8 tons ha⁻¹) was obtained by combined administration of cattle manure and nitrogen fertilizer at the concentrations of 20 tons ha⁻¹ and 150 kg N ha⁻¹, respectively. So, the integrated use of cattle manure and nitrogen fertilizer could be a suitable solution for achieving optimum growth characteristics and subsequently increased tuber yield.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors are grateful to M. R. Najm, Z. Banihashemi, and Islamic Azad University, Roudehen Branch, for their financial support to the present project. The authors thank E. Panahi, and the faculty members of the Agriculture Islamic Azad University, Roudehen Branch.

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